

CHARGE AND STABILITY OF COLLOIDS. PART V. POTENTIOMETRIC TITRATIONS OF CHROMIUM HYDROXIDE SOL

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In this paper the release of chlorine ions from the counter part of the double layer in Cr_2O_3 sols, prepared by adding ammonia to CrCl_3 , has been studied by the slow potentiometric titration method. It has been found that the amount of chlorine released from the Cr_2O_3 sol like that of Fe_2O_3 and Al_2O_3 sols depends on the purity of the sol.

A theoretical explanation for the super-equivalent release of the chlorine, based on the electrical adsorption of these ions on the surface of the colloidal particles of the hydrous oxide sols, has been advanced.

In previous communications of this series (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 20, 25, 110, 115, 120) it has been shown that super-equivalent amount of chlorine is displaced from ferric hydroxide and aluminium hydroxide hydrosols on the addition of multivalent coagulating ions when the sols are not sufficiently pure. With the progress of dialysis and the consequent increase in purity a point is reached after which an amount of chlorine less than the added electrolyte is released from both the above mentioned sols.

In this paper chromium hydroxide hydrosols, prepared by the addition of ammonia to chromium chloride is studied. The displacement of chlorine ions from the counter part of the double layer is measured potentiometrically as in the previous papers (*loc. cit.*) by an arrangement similar to that adopted by Weiser (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1943, 35, 1).

EXPERIMENTAL

The experimental procedure followed in this paper is just the same as described in the previous communications of this series of papers (*loc. cit.*). The chromium hydroxide sol was prepared by taking about 80 g. of chromium chloride and dissolving it in freshly prepared distilled water and diluting the solution to about 4 litres. Dilute ammonia was added drop by drop followed by thorough shaking of the solution after each addition of drop of ammonia till the sol was just short of precipitation. The solution was left overnight and filtered the next morning. A small portion of the solution was kept aside for potentiometric titrations with the undialysed sol and the rest was kept for progressive dialysis in two Neidle dialysers. Samples of the sol at different purity were taken out from the dialysers after every sixth day and each sample titrated by step-wise addition of the electrolytes. The results obtained have been given in the following tables and shown graphically in Fig. 1. To economise space only two tables are given. Seven different samples of the sol have been titrated with KNO_3 , K_2SO_4 , and K-citrate but results with two sols only are recorded.

DISCUSSION

From the tables given below it is clear that Cr_2O_3 sol also behaves in a manner similar to those of Fe_2O_3 and Al_2O_3 sols (*vide* previous publications, *loc. cit.*).

TABLE I
Sol III.

Cr_2O_3 sol = 6.01 g./litre. Chlorine = 0.0643 g. ions/litre. Purity* of the sol = 93.49. Temp. = 25°.

	v.	ecl.	Chlorine $\times 10^3$		
			Total.	Displaced.	Equiv. to ppt ion added.
KNO ₃ (N)					
0.00 c.c	0.0403 volts	16.52×10^{-3}	18.42	0.00	0.00
2.00	0.0328	22.13	25.46	6.84	100.00
5.00	0.0310	23.74	27.19	8.77	250.00
7.00	0.0306	24.12	27.69	9.27	350.00
K ₂ SO ₄ (N/20)					
1.00	0.0369	18.87	21.15	2.73	2.50
2.00	0.0335	21.54	24.32	5.90	5.00
3.50	0.0294	25.28	28.92	10.50	8.75
5.50	0.0266	28.18	32.54	14.12	13.75
K citrate (N/50)					
2.00	0.0368	18.94	21.25	2.83	2.00
4.00	0.0348	20.48	20.09	4.67	4.00
6.00	0.0329	22.05	25.00	6.58	6.00
8.00	0.0294	25.28	28.88	10.46	8.00

TABLE II
Sol IV.

Cr_2O_3 sol = 5.83 g./litre. Chlorine = 0.0361 g. ions/litre. Purity* of the sol = 161.50. Temp. = 25°.

	v.	ecl.	Chlorine $\times 10^{-3}$		
			Total.	Displaced.	Equiv. to ppt ion added.
KNO ₃ (N)					
0.00	0.0571 volts	8.50×10^{-3}	9.38	0.00	0.00
2.00	0.0480	12.25	23.52	4.14	100.00
4.00	0.0460	13.24	14.67	5.29	200.00
6.00	0.0454	13.55	15.06	5.68	300.00
K ₂ SO ₄ (N/20)					
1.00	0.0515	10.77	11.87	2.46	2.50
2.00	0.0479	12.30	13.57	4.19	5.00
3.50	0.0430	14.87	16.53	7.15	8.75
K-citrate (N/50)					
2.00	0.0539	9.73	10.66	1.28	2.00
5.00	0.0470	12.73	14.00	4.71	5.00
7.00	0.0452	13.66	15.16	5.78	7.00

* Purity of the sol in the tables refers to the ratio of Cr_2O_3 to chlorine content of the sol.

The following table gives the relation between purity and chlorine displaced from Cr_2O_3 sol as used herein.

TABLE III

Sol.	Conc. of sol per litre.	Chlorine content of the sol per litre.	Cr_2O_3 Cl	Nature of displacement of Cl.
I	6.78 g.	0.2155 g. ions	31.46	Super equiv.
II	6.16	0.1197	51.46	"
III	6.01	0.0643	93.49	"
IV	5.83	0.0361	161.50	Less than equiv.
V	5.64	0.0214	263.50	"
VI	5.58	0.0132	422.30	"
VII	5.52	0.0099	557.50	"

From this it is clear that the same sol begins to release less Cl than equivalent of electrolyte added as soon as its purity reaches a certain point.

Super-equivalent Displacement of Chlorine Ions

In order to explain the super-equivalent release of chlorine ions on coagulation of the sol it is necessary to bear in mind that such release of Cl ions is associated with the presence of considerable amount of the impurity in the inter-micellary liquid. On account of this, Cl is present in such a form as not to be determinable potentiometrically. On neutralisation of the charge on the colloid this osmotically inactive Cl becomes active. This inactive chlorine is different from the fixed Cl which constitutes the rigid portion of the outer part of the double layer. The Cl ions from the rigid portion of the counter ions can in no account be more than what is equivalent to the total charge on the colloidal particle and which is measured by the amount of the coagulating ion added to the sol provided it is completely adsorbed by the sol. But since an amount of Cl, super-equivalent to the added polyvalent coagulating ions is released it is certain that fixed chlorine is in two different states *i.e.*, one which constitutes the rigid portion of the counter part of the double layer, and the other which is present on the surface of the colloid as ion pairs. This means that the surface of the colloidal particle contains both positive and negative ions as ion pairs, a part of which is ionised to give an effective positive charge to the surface.

On the basis of the above observations a mechanism of coagulation is suggested below which explains the super-equivalent release of chlorine ions from the hydrous oxide sols.

Mechanism of Coagulation of Hydrous Oxide Sols

From the foregoing results it appears that when, say, the Fe_2O_3 sol is impure, the surface of the colloid is covered with Fe^{+++} and H^+ ions as the primary adsorbed ions to give an effective

positive charge to the colloid, and also with ion pairs such as Fe and Cl as well as H and Cl ions. With progress of dialysis the electrically adsorbed ions forming the unionised ion pairs are ionised due to the washing away of chlorine ions from the surface and thus the positively charged ions are left on the surface and so the charge on the surface continually increases. This is supported by the experimental results of Mukherjee, Chaudhury and Ghosh (*Trans. Nat. Inst. Sci. India*, 1935, 1, 47) and Desai and Borker (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1923, 29, 1269). Thus with progressively pure sols the quantity of chlorine held on the surface as unionised ion pairs decreases. Hence the amount of super-equivalent release of chlorine ions becomes less and less as the intermicellary liquid becomes purer and purer, as is shown by the general form of the curves in Fig. 1.

The mechanism of coagulation of the hydrous oxide sols on the addition of electrolytes can also have an explanation in the light of the above considerations :

On addition of electrolytes to the less pure sols a super-equivalent release of Cl ions has been observed. Evidently the coagulating ion, when it penetrates the double layer displaces some chlorine ions from its outer part and this at the best can be equivalent to the amount of the polyvalent ion added provided it is completely adsorbed. In addition to this, as the coagulating ion penetrates the double layer and reaches near enough the surface the charge density on the surface is reduced and thus the electrically adsorbed ions, which were held on the surface of the micelle, are released now owing to low surface density. This produces a super-equivalent release of Cl ions. When, however, the Cl ions, which were electrically held on the surface, are released, the surface should become more positively charged. This view is corroborated from the experimental results of Rabinowitsch and Fodimann (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1932, 159, 403), who observed an increase in the cataphoretic speed of the particles of a sol which displaced super-equivalent amount of Cl ions, on the addition of 0.5N-Na₂SO₄ solution to Fe₂O₃ sol.

With the progress of dialysis the possibility of getting more Cl ions from the surface of the micelle becomes less, because, as the sol is dialysed the surface becomes more and more free from the ion pairs and thus the release of the Cl ions from the electrically held ion pairs on the surface becomes less and therefore at a certain stage of dialysis the super-equivalent release of Cl ions from the micelles on the addition of polyvalent electrolytes ceases and Cl released after that critical stage of dialysis of the sol is always less than the equivalent of the electrolytes added to the sol.

At that stage of dialysis, where the super-equivalent release of Cl ions ceases, one cannot say that the surface of the colloid has been completely freed from the unionised ion pairs. There may be some of the ion pairs still left on the surface and may be sparsely situated and may be comparatively very few in number when compared with the surface of the less pure sols. On addition of electrolytes these ion pairs lose their Cl ions and thus instead of being held in pairs are now left alone on the surface and thus impart a positive charge to the sol. This is supported by the data of Rabinowitsch and Fodimann (*loc. cit.*) from the observed increase in the cataphoretic speed of the particles of Fe₂O₃ sol which displaced Cl less than the equivalent of the added electrolyte.

In spite of this extra-release of the Cl ions, the possibility of which is not completely debarred, super-equivalent release of Cl does not occur as the quantity of electrically held Cl, which is released from the surface, is small and is probably less than the amount of Cl present in the diffused portion of the outer component of the double layer. So, although there may be an increase in the surface density due to release of comparatively small electrically held Cl ions on the surface, this release may not be sufficiently large to make up for that portion of the double layer and are osmotically active.

The increase in the cataphoretic speed of the colloidal particles in those sols which displace Cl ions less than the equivalent was very small when compared with the percentage increase with those sols which displace super-equivalent amount of the Cl ions.